

BAFFLING INCONSISTENCIES BETWEEN WORK ENGAGEMENT AND JOB BURNOUT: THE POTENTIAL MEDIATION OF ORGANIZATION ENGAGEMENT - INSIGHTS FROM A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Purpose: The evolutionary course of the relationship between work engagement and burnout reveals a pattern of inconsistencies and unpredictability. Furthermore, despite numerous studies **attempting** to explain this intricate interplay, the role of **organization** engagement, a related yet significantly separate construct, is **inexplicably** overlooked. This systematic literature review explores the evolving relationship between work engagement and burnout, considering contextual variables, and also answers the question: what role does **organization** engagement play in the inconsistent relationship? **Research methodology/approach:** The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) framework has been adopted in this systematic literature review, considering relevant peer-reviewed empirical articles from the Scopus database. **Findings:** The paper has presented a novel conceptual framework with organizational engagement as a mediating variable between work engagement and job burnout. It has delineated numerous moderating and mediating variables that influence the relationship between work engagement and job burnout, which may possibly be the reason for the dynamic relationship between them, varying from being negative, positive, curvilinear, and coexisting. **Originality/value:** This paper fills the gap in extant literature by proposing the potential mediation of organization engagement between work engagement and burnout. Additionally, it provides practitioners with valuable insights, highlighting the significant role that organization engagement plays in enhancing employee work engagement.

Keywords: Work Engagement, Job Engagement, Employee Engagement, Organization Engagement, Burnout, Job Burnout.

INTRODUCTION

Work engagement aligns with the model of positive psychology which entails an effective combination of commitment, productivity, loyalty, and ownership attitude among the employees towards their work (González-Romá et al., 2006). It is said to be a precursor to employee well-being, that boosts productivity (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014), reduces employee's intentions to quit (Juhdi et al., 2013), and enhances better work-life balance (Albdour & Altarawneh, 2014). However, the absence of work engagement can cause ill-being and lead to chronic job stress, resulting in job burnout. The debate regarding the relationship between work engagement and burnout continues due to the baffling inconsistency observed between them. After decades of research, the inconsistent correlation includes negative (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004; Freney & Tiernan, 2006), positive (Garrad & Chamorro-Premuzic, 2016; Halbesleben, 2010; Geurts & Demerouti, 2003; Bakker et al., 2011), curvilinear (Yang et al., 2022), and co-existing relationships (Salmela-Aro et al., 2019; Abos et al., 2019; Moodie et al., 2014; Skinner & Roche, 2021; Nerstad et al., 2019).

The perplexity deepens with the findings that work engagement and organization engagement are distinct constructs. Initially, the concept of employee engagement pertained to the engagement of employees to both their specific work tasks and the overarching organizational objectives (Kahn, 1990). Subsequently, Saks (2006) introduced a conceptual distinction by delineating employee engagement into work and organization engagement which is specific to the role that is under consideration. Saks' (2022) comprehensive comparative review reinforced Andrew & Sofian's (2012) significant finding of a moderate correlation between work and organization engagement through a paired t-test. Despite the observed significant differences between the two constructs, the prevailing focus within the engagement literature has predominantly centered on work engagement, as evidenced by the common usage of the term "work engagement," which is often associated with the UWES (Utrecht Work Engagement Scale) measure of engagement (Rai & Maheshwari 2020). Work engagement exclusively addresses the employee's connection to their specific work, neglecting the broader aspect of their engagement with the organization. In contrast, Saks (2006) and Saks and Gruman (2014) contended that an employee might exhibit engagement in organizational activities while concurrently experiencing disengagement from their specific job, or vice versa. Consequently, relying solely on the measurement of work engagement may yield a contaminated measure of engagement, complicating the interpretation and generalization of findings (Saks, 2019). Previous research has focused on the antecedents and consequences of work engagement, showing a causal link with organization engagement (Rai & Maheshwari, 2020). However, little focus has been given to the simultaneous inclusion of both work and organization engagement in a unified model, exploration of the relationship between organization engagement and burnout, and the possible role of organization engagement in the relationship between work engagement and burnout are notably lacking. Consequently, to provide actionable insights to employers for fostering engagement among their employees, it is imperative to investigate the role of organization engagement in the relationship between work engagement and burnout. This study systematically reviews the literature to:

- 1) Explore the dynamic correlation between job burnout and work engagement, taking into account contextual variables and
- 2) Investigate the specific role of organization engagement in the dynamic relationship between job burnout and work engagement.

This paper begins with an overview of the concepts, followed by an explanation of the methodology used, a presentation of the main findings aligned with the previously mentioned research objective, and concludes by proposing a conceptual framework and future research agenda.

Overview of the Constructs

Work Engagement

The engagement literature can be broadly divided into two work engagement and organization engagement. Work engagement is categorized as the extent to which employees are exclusively engrossed with their specific jobs (Shuck et al., 2017). It focuses on an individual's psychological condition during the performance of a particular task (Purcell, 2014). The most widely accepted definition of work engagement defines it to be "a positive, fulfilling work-related state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption" (Schaufeli et al., 2002). As work

engagement is specific to one's job task, it is a narrow approach that primarily concentrates on employees' work activities (Kossyva et al., 2022).

Organization Engagement

Organization engagement is defined as the emotional and intellectual commitment of an employee to their organization (Farndale et al., 2014; Guest, 2014; Saks, 2006). It pertains to the attitudes, intentions, and actions exhibited by employees in their interactions with the organization (Saks, 2006). Therefore, "to measure organization engagement the target of the items must be the organization" (Saks, 2019). According to Saks (2006) work and organization engagement are interconnected yet separate constructs, characterized by differences in their underlying factors and outcomes. Additionally, organization engagement exhibits a greater predictive utility of organizational outcomes than work engagement. This suggests that organization engagement elucidates a significant portion of the variance in work-related outcomes beyond what can be attributed to work engagement.

Burnout

Burnout was introduced by Freudenberger (1974) as a slow physical and emotional depletion that leads to lesser commitment to work and productivity. It is also defined as a severe work-related strain that induces mental, physical, and organizational outcomes, that are negatively represented by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and diminished personal accomplishment (Halbesleben & Buckley, 2004; Karatepe, 2013; Karatepe & Ehsani, 2012). When organizations raise the bar of productivity, performance, and quality, the possibility of achieving the goals lies with the human capital, specifically with the nature and extent of employee engagement (Baldoni, 2013). Burnout is a negative response arising from stress on the job. Both personal and organizational factors influence the occurrence of burnout. On one end of the continuum, there exist intrinsic elements within individuals that render them susceptible to burnout (Maslach et al., 2001). However, an alternative perspective contends that the causes of burnout are external, highlighting the significant role played by organizational systems and management in shaping conditions conducive to employee burnout (Freudenberger, 1977; Maslach & Leiter, 1997). Therefore, it is crucial to examine burnout separately within both individual and organizational contexts. Engagement and burnout hold great significance for individuals and organizations. When appropriately leveraged, they can boost productivity and performance, but improper management can result in setbacks (Awa et al., 2010). The researcher attempts to explore through the available empirical studies, the conflicting relationship between engagement and burnout.

METHODOLOGY

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) (Page et al., 2021) is adopted in this systematic review. Relevant peer-reviewed research stocks were retrieved from the Scopus database (only Q1 and Q2 journals).

Scopus is a popular and comprehensive database which is house to 75 million published records and offers accurate citation searches (Baas et al., 2020). A combination of keywords was used for the retrieval of relevant research stock by following (Talwar et al., 2020). Screening results found that the most frequently used keywords in the papers' titles, abstracts, and keyword lists are 'engagement', 'work engagement', 'job engagement', 'employee engagement', 'organization engagement',

‘organizational engagement’, AND ‘burnout’, ‘job burnout’, ‘job stress’. An information search was done from published studies from the period 2002 to 2022 for journal articles published in the English language. Our search yielded 1022 research documents which were screened for their relevance and quality and other exclusion and inclusion criteria. The detailed data retrieval flowchart is detailed in Figure 1. We finally used a set of 75 empirical papers based on the scope and relevance of this study to develop the theme of this paper.

Figure 1: Flowchart based on the PRISMA framework (following Page et al., 2021)

FINDINGS

From eligible research papers, we selected the information from the measures, hypothesis testing, and discussion sections of each article. The purpose of the study was to identify research papers and highlight the inconsistent correlation between work engagement and burnout in the presence or absence of contextual variables.

Concerning the first research question, we specifically recorded the nature of the relationship between work engagement and burnout and categorized them based on their correlation. Addressing the second research question, we have highlighted the role of mediators and moderators in the relationship between work engagement and burnout. Mentioned below is the thematic analysis based on the relationship between work engagement and burnout of the 75 articles included in this study. Four themes (negative, curvilinear, positive, and co-existence) were majorly found to explain the inconsistent correlation between work engagement and burnout.

Negative Correlation between work engagement and burnout:

The negative correlation between work engagement and burnout highlights the inverse relationship between active involvement in work and exhaustion resulting from job burnout mentioned below is Table 1. which shows the negative correlation between work engagement and burnout.

Table 1: Negative correlation between work engagement and burnout:

S. No	Author	Year	Journal	Relationship	Mediator	Moderator	Theory
1	Tan K.-L., Yeap P.F.	2022	Management Decision (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	COR & JD-R
2	Kordsmeyer A.-C., Efimov I., Harth V., Maché S.	2022	BMJ Open (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
3	Cacciamani S., Cesareni D., Fiorilli C., Ligorio M.B.	2022	Education Sciences (Q1)	Negative	ICT training technologies	NA	Theory not mentioned
4	Chambel M.J., Carvalho V.S.	2022	Frontiers in Psychology (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	COR
5	Teoh K.B., Kee D.M.H.	2022	International Journal of Trade and Global Market (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	COR & JD-R
6	Fute A., Sun B., Oubibi M.	2022	Psychology Research and Behaviour Management (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	Theory not mentioned
7	Evans K., Papinniemi A., Vuvan V., Nicholson V., Dafny H., Levy T., Chipchase L.	2022	Psychotherapy Theory and Practice (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	Theory not mentioned
8	Mohamed S.A., Hendy A., Ezzat Mahmoud O., Mohamed Mohamed S.	2022	Nursing Open (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	Theory not mentioned
9	Yansane A., Tokede O., Walji M., Obadan-Udoh E., Riedy C., White J., Kalenderian E.	2021	Journal of Patient Safety (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	Theory not mentioned
10	Dai Y.-D., Zhuang W.-L., Lu S.-C., Huan T.-C.	2021	Tourism Review (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	Social Identity Theory
11	Oosthuizen R.M., Mayer C.-H., Zwane N.J.	2021	South Asian Journal of Human Resource Management (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	Theory not mentioned
12	Edna Rabenu, Or Shkoler, Mariana J. Lebron, Filiz Tabak	2019	Current Psychology (Q2)	Negative correlation but not significant	Heavy work investment and Time Commitment	NA	JD-R

13	<i>Ivanovic T., Ivancevic S., Maricic M.</i>	2020	Engineering Economics (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	Not mentioned
14	<i>Mette J., Robelski S., Wirth T., Nienhaus A., Harth V., Mache S.</i>	2020	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
15	<i>Contreras F., Espinosa J.C., Esguerra G.A.</i>	2020	Sage Open (Q1)	Work engagement and burnout are separate constructs with a negative correlation	NA	NA	COR
16	<i>Salmela-Aro K., Upadyaya K.</i>	2018	Journal of Vocational Behaviour (Q1)	Work engagement and burnout are separate but negatively correlated constructs	NA	High resilience	JD-R
17	<i>Faskhodi A.A., Siyyari M.</i>	2018	Australian Journal of Teacher Education (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	Not mentioned
18	<i>Loerbroks A., Glaser J., Vu-Eickmann P., Angerer P.</i>	2017	Occupational Medicine (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	Not mentioned
19	<i>Maricuțoiu L.P., Sulea C., Iancu A.</i>	2107	Burnout Research	Negative	NA	Time lag	Broad and Build COR theory
20	<i>Mäkikangas A., Hyvönen K., Feldt T.</i>	2017	Burnout Research	Negative	NA	NA	Social cognitive career theory
21	<i>Van Den Broeck A., Elst T.V., Baillien E., Sercu M., Schouteden M., De Witte H., Godderis L.</i>	2017	Journal of occupational and Environmental Medicine (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
22	<i>Upadyaya K., Vartiainen M., Salmela-Aro K.</i>	2016	Burnout Research	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R & COR
23	<i>Lo Bue S., Taverniers J., Mylle J., Euwema M.</i>	2013	Journal of Career Development (Q1)	Opposite	NA	Individual difference (Hardiness) moderates between WE & BO	Self-determination theory
24	<i>Crawford E.R., LePine J.A., Rich B.L.</i>	2010	Journal of Applied Psychology (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R

25	<i>Korunka C., Kubicek B., Schaufeli W.B., Hoonakker P.</i>	2009	Journal of Positive Psychology (Q1)	Moderately Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
26	<i>Hakanen J.J., Schaufeli W.B., Ahola K.</i>	2008	Work and Stress (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
27	<i>Te Brake H., Bouman A.-M., Gorter R., Hoogstraten J., Eijkman M.</i>	2007	European Journal of Oral Sciences (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	Not mentioned
28	<i>González-Romá V., Schaufeli W.B., Bakker A.B., Lloret S.</i>	2006	Journal of Vocational Behaviour (Q1)	Work engagement and burnout are conceptually opposite	NA	NA	Not mentioned
29	<i>Langelaan S., Bakker A.B., van Doornen L.J.P., Schaufeli W.B.</i>	2006	Personality and Individual Differences (Q1)	Work engagement and burnout are each other's opposite	NA	NA	JD-R
30	<i>Hakanen J.J., Koivumäki J.</i>	2014	Burnout Research	Negative	NA	NA	Broad and Build Theory
31	<i>Hakanen J.J., Bakker A.B., Schaufeli W.B.</i>	2006	Journal of School Psychology (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JDC COR & JD-R
32	<i>van den Broeck A., de Cuyper N., de Witte H., Vansteenkiste M.</i>	2010	European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
33	<i>Bakker A.B., Van Emmerik H., Euwema M.C.</i>	2006	Work and Occupations (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
34	<i>Calvo J.M., Kwatra J., Yansane A., Tokede O., Gorter R.C., Kalenderian E.</i>	2021	Journal of Patient Safety (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	Not mentioned
35	<i>Taris T.W., Ybema J.F., Beek I.V.</i>	2017	Burnout Research	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	JD-R
36	<i>Trépanier S.-G., Fernet C., Austin S., Ménard J.</i>	2015	Burnout Research	Separate Constructs with over-lapping dimensions	NA	NA	JD-R
37	<i>Demerouti E., Mostert K., Bakker A.B.</i>	2010	Journal of Occupational Health and Psychology	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	JD-R

38	<i>Ogbonnaya U.C., Thiese M.S., Allen J.</i>	2022	Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine (Q2)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	Not mentioned
39	<i>Hagen T., Bogaerts S., De Caluwé E.</i>	2023	Psychiatry, Psychology, and Law (Q1)	Work engagement and Burnout are strongly negative. Still, the lack of professional efficacy dimension was found to be strongly correlated to work engagement instead of burnout.	NA	NA	Not mentioned
40	<i>Rożnowski B.</i>	2020	Annals of Psychology	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
41	<i>Trógolo M.A., Morera L.P., Castellano E., Spontón C., Medrano L.A.</i>	2020	European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology (Q1)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	Dialectical Theory
42	<i>Nimon K., Shuck B.</i>	2020	Human Resource Development Quarterly (Q1)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	Self-determination theory and JD-R theory
43	<i>Fernández I., Enrique S., Santos S.D.L., Tomás J.M.</i>	2020	Testing, Psychometrics, Methodology in Applied Psychology (Q2)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	JD-R
44	<i>Goering D.D., Shimazu A., Zhou F., Wada T., Sakai R.</i>	2017	Burnout Research	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	JD-R
45	<i>Hakanen J.J., Schaufeli W.B.</i>	2012	Journal of Affective Disorders (Q1)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	COR
46	<i>Cole M.S., Walter F., Bedeian A.G., O'Boyle E.H.</i>	2012	Journal of Management (Q1)	Work engagement and burnout are bipolar opposites	NA	NA	JD-R
47	<i>Chirkowska-Smolak T.</i>	2012	Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behaviour (Q1)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	Karasek's expanded model of stress. (Job

							demand control/stress) or (JD-R)
48	<i>Mäkikangas A., Feldt T., Kinnunen U., Tolvanen A.</i>	2012	Anxiety, Stress, and Coping (Q1)	The correlation between work engagement and burnout is dependent on their sub-dimensions. Work engagement fluctuates depending upon its interaction with the sub-dimensions of burnout.	NA	NA	Not mentioned
49	<i>Kim H.J., Shin K.H., Swanger N.</i>	2009	International Journal of Hospitality Management (Q1)	Engagement and burnout are two separate concepts.	NA	NA	Big-Five personality dimensions
50	<i>Tu B., Luo X., Sitar S., Huang C.</i>	2022	Frontiers in Public Health	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
51	<i>Llorens S., Salanova M., Chambel M.J., Torrente P., Ângelo R.P.</i>	2022	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health (1)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	Proactive coping	NA	JD-R
52	<i>Moyano N., Perez-Yus M.C., Herrera-Mercadal P., Navarro-Gil M., Valle S., Montero-Marin J.</i>	2021	Current Psychology (Q2)	Negative	Intrapersonal Mindfulness	NA	JD-R
53	<i>Van Steenbergen E.F., van der Ven C., Peeters M.C.W., Taris T.W.</i>	2018	Psychological Reports (Q2)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NWW and PsyCap had some moderating effects between engagement and burnout.	JD-R
54	<i>Kotze M.</i>	2018	African Journal of Economic and Management Studies (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
55	<i>Hakanen J.J., Seppälä P., Peeters M.C.W.</i>	2017	International Journal of Behavioural Medicine (Q2)	Negative	NA	Job crafting moderates the negative	JD-R

						effect of job demands on burnout and, to a lesser extent, on WE	
56	<i>García-Sierra R., Fernández-Castro J., Martínez-Zaragoza F.</i>	2016	Journal of Nursing Management (Q1)	Separate constructs with differing dimensional level correlation	NA	NA	JD-R
57	<i>Wu T.-J., Yuan K.-S., Yen D.C., Yeh C.-F.</i>	2022	European Management Journal (Q1)	Negative	NA	Emotional Support, and instrumental support	JDC
58	<i>Chen C.-F., Chen S.-C.</i>	2012	International Journal of Aviation Psychology (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
59	<i>Lee R.S., Son Hing L.S., Gnanakumaran V., Weiss S.K., Lero D.S., Hausdorf P.A., Daneman D.</i>	2021	Frontiers in Psychology (Q2)	Separate constructs with only the exhaustion component of burnout negatively associated with work engagement	NA	NA	JD_R
60	<i>Lachowska B., Minda K.</i>	2020	Archives of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy (Q2)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
61	<i>Cotter E.W., Fouad N.A.</i>	2013	Journal of Career Development (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R
62	<i>WILMAR B. SCHAUFELI* AND ARNOLD B. BAKKER</i>	2004	Journal of Organizational Behaviour (Q1)	Negative	NA	NA	JD-R

Our analysis found that 4 studies reported engagement and burnout to be conceptually opposite, they represent contrasting states, where the presence of one construct implies the absence of another and vice-versa. Moreover, 40 studies have reported a negative correlation between work engagement and burnout. This inverse correlation ranged between -.15 to -.65 (Schaufeli, 2013): as work engagement goes up, burnout tends to go down and as burnout increases, work engagement tends to decrease. Additionally, 18 studies have reported engagement and burnout to be separate but related constructs, with correlation ranging from significant to an insignificant negative correlation between either of the dimensions of work engagement and burnout.

Curvilinear Correlation between work engagement and burnout:

Mentioned below is Table 2, which shows a curvilinear correlation between work engagement and burnout.

Table 2: Curvilinear correlation between work engagement and burnout:

49	Yang G., Wei H., Wan L., Dong H., Liang X., He Y.	2022	Frontiers in Public Health (Q2)	Curvilinear	NA	External monitoring by supervisors	Not mentioned
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Table 2

One study reported a curvilinear correlation between work engagement and burnout. The prevalent notion that individuals with high engagement are inherently safeguarded against burnout neglects the findings of a subset of studies, indicating a curvilinear pattern. This pattern introduces a more nuanced view, suggesting that the positive impact of engagement may be contingent on an optimal level, beyond which it could potentially revert to negative consequences (Yang et al. 2022).

Positive Correlation between work engagement and burnout:

Work engagement and burnout being two independent constructs may be positively correlated depending upon the context and the interacting variables, mentioned below is Table 3, which represents the studies with a positive correlation between work engagement and burnout.

Table 3: Positive correlation between work engagement and burnout

1	Upadyaya K., Salmela-Aro K.	2020	Anxiety, Stress, and Coping (Q1)	Positive	NA	NA	JD-R
2	Nickum M., Desrumaux P.	2023	Psychiatry, Psychology, and Law (Q1)	Over-engagement is positively correlated with burnout	NA	NA	JD-R
3	Salmela-Aro K., Hietajärvi L., Lonka K.	2019	Frontiers in Psychology (Q2)	Positive co-occurrence of engagement and burnout	NA	NA	JD-R
4	Nerstad C.G.L., Wong S.I., Richardsen A.M.	2019	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health (Q1)	Positive correlation Engagement fuels burnout when it exceeds a certain level	NA	Perceived motivational climate	COR Achievement goal theory and Work engagement theory
5	Timms C., Brough P., Graham D.	2012	Journal of Educational Administration (Q1)	Positively correlated in groups working under pressure	NA	NA	Not mentioned
6	Sonnentag S., Binnewies C., Mojza E.J.	2010	Journal of Applied Psychology (Q1)	Positively correlated	NA	Failed detachment from work during off-job time.	JD-R
7	Akinola A.A.	2020	Psychology and Practice	Positive correlation	NA	NA	JD-R

Table 3

7 studies reported engagement and burnout to be positively correlated, it is crucial to note that engagement and burnout are not fixed states or intrinsic traits, but rather potential outcomes influenced by task performance and exhibiting variability across diverse tasks (Sonnetag, 2017). The inverse correlation between work engagement and burnout is not constant in all combinations; there are instances where employees encounter diverse levels of exhaustion and vigor that deviate from the anticipated negative correlation (Makikangas et al., 2017). Employees exhibiting high levels of engagement may concurrently endure an average level of burnout (Rao et al., 2020).

Co-existence of work engagement and burnout:

Work engagement and burnout are not two endpoints of a continuum however, they produce negative relationships that vary from moderate to strong this introduces the possibility of individuals experiencing engagement and burnout simultaneously (Timms et al., 2012), mentioned below is Table 4 which highlights the studies with the coexistence of engagement and burnout.

Table 4: Co-existence of work engagement and burnout.

1	Rao S.K., Ferris T.G., Hidrue M.K., Lehrhoff S.R., Lenz S., Heffernan J., McKee K.E., Del Carmen M.G.	2020	Clinical Medicine and Research (Q2)	Four distinct engaged and burnout profiles	NA	NA	Theory not mentioned
2	Vaart L., de Beer L.T.	2021	International Journal of Wellbeing (Q1)	Five distinct burnout and engagement profiles.	NA	NA	JD-R
3	Salmela-Aro K., Hietajärvi L., Lonka K.	2019	Frontiers in Psychology (Q2)	Positive co-occurrence of engagement and burnout	NA	NA	JD-R
4	Jugale P.V., Mallaiah P., Krishnamurthy A., Sangha R.	2016	Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research	Positive correlation and co-exist.	NA	NA	Not mentioned
5	Gillet N., Morin A.J.S., Blais A.-R.	2022	Group and Organization Management (Q1)	Five different engagement burnout profiles: positive correlation, co-occur, negative correlation	NA	NA	JD-R

Table 4

5 studies have reported engagement and burnout to co-exist. The linear linkage established in prior research between work engagement and burnout inadequately captures the nuanced dynamics inherent in their association (Vaart & de Beer, 2021). According to the "Too much of a good thing effect" principle (Pierce & Aguinis, 2013) and the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory (Hobfoll, 2018), when employees surpass a specific threshold of engagement, they become more vulnerable to burnout.

Employees who exhibit excessive work engagement without psychological detachment are at an elevated risk of experiencing burnout (Gillet et al., 2022; Nerstad et al., 2019; Timms et al., 2012; Sonnentag et al., 2010). While being highly engaged in one's work may initially appear advantageous, however, it renders employees more susceptible to an increased risk of burnout. Consequently, becoming excessively absorbed in work while neglecting other life domains results in the co-existence of engagement and burnout (Moeller et al., 2018; Nerstad et al., 2019).

The inconsistent correlation between work engagement and burnout can be attributed to the context in wherein the work takes place. Various contextual variables alleviate or enhance the effect of engagement and burnout among individuals (Sonnentag et al., 2010). Mentioned below are some of the contextual variables that have mediated or moderated between engagement and burnout.

Mediators and Moderators Between Work Engagement and Burnout:

Given the inconsistent nature of the association between work engagement and burnout, the dynamics of this relationship vary based on interacting variables. Mentioned below in Figure 2 are the contextual variables that have mediated or moderated the relationship between work engagement and burnout.

Figure 2: Mediators and Moderators between work engagement and burnout:

The presence of mediators or moderators can influence the impact of work engagement on burnout or vice-versa. The inconsistent correlation between work engagement and burnout is a result of the mediators or moderators working as interacting variables such as heavy work investment despite being positively correlated to work engagement (Rabenu et al. 2021) can contribute to burnout when individuals experience exhaustion without sufficient opportunities for recovery. This implies that forcing heavy work investment on employees with high work engagement may lead to burnout which is the reason the negative correlation between engagement and burnout was not significant. Other mediating variables such as pro-active coping strategies, use of ICT in one's job, and inter and intra-mindfulness were found to have a mediating effect between engagement and burnout. The correlation between work engagement and burnout remained negative in the presence of these mediating variables, which establishes the importance of these variables for maintaining a balance between the two continuums.

Other contextual variables that moderated the relationship between work engagement were also seen to influence the pre-existing negative correlation. Except two moderating variables i.e., failed detachment from job during of-the-job-time and perceived motivational climates which influenced a positive correlation between both engagement and burnout, rest other moderating variables were found to influence a negative correlation.

DISCUSSION

This study addressed two research objectives, the first RO: the dynamic correlation between job burnout and work engagement, taking into account contextual variables, and the second RO: investigated the role of organization engagement between work engagement and burnout. While earlier studies have explored the correlation between work engagement and burnout, they have not explicitly addressed the reason for this baffling inconsistency and the role of organization engagement between work engagement and burnout has also not been explored.

Through this systematic review, we found that the relationship between work engagement and burnout varied from being negative, to positive, curvilinear (Trogolo et al., 2020), and co-existing (Moeller et al., 2019). Given that the relationship between the constructs is not linear, the fluctuations in their correlation are contingent and reliant upon factors that offer a motivational mechanism that interacts between them (Maricutoiu et al., 2017; Nimon & Shuck, 2019). While work engagement and burnout share a strong relationship, it's each dimension provides distinct contributions (Makikanga et al., 2012). According to Yang et al. (2022), the dimensional measurement of engagement and burnout states that the relationship between "work engagement", "depersonalization", and "personal accomplishment" follows a U-shaped curve, indicating a curvilinear association between work engagement and burnout. This states that work engagement and burnout are not only inversely correlated, but there can be other correlations too. Likewise, Kahn (2013) gave an example of his field research (personal interview, February 19, 2013), where he witnessed exhausted healthcare workers who were highly engaged during the treatment of their patients, despite showing all the symptoms of burnout. The example of Kahn is a piece of evidence that engagement is not only followed by vigor and dedication but can also be accompanied by exhaustion and cynicism (McMann et al., 2017). The vigor among the exhausted healthcare workers can be due to the

contextual environment wherein they were working. This contradicts the findings of the JD-R model (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004), which indicates that job resources facilitate work engagement, while job demands contribute to the development of job burnout. According to the JD-R Model, job resources and job demands follow an inverse correlation which is evident in the relationship between work engagement and burnout (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Through this review, we found that work engagement and burnout do not necessarily follow an inverse correlation. As highlighted by (Crawford et al., 2010) challenging job demands can be positively correlated with work engagement. Therefore, it's not necessary that work engagement can only be negatively correlated with burnout, there can be a positive correlation between the two if there exists a challenging job demand along with adequate job resources. Work engagement and burnout are reliant upon the contextual factors that provide meaning to them. Factors such as failing to detach oneself from work during the off-job time and perceived motivational climate were two moderating variables that influenced a positive correlation between work engagement and burnout. Similarly, heavy work investment is another mediating variable that shows, that despite being positively correlated with work engagement it has a positive correlation with burnout too. This indicates that the relationship between both work engagement and burnout is contextual and cannot be considered to be inverse all the time. Therefore, there is a need to look for more contextual and organizational factors that impact the relationship between work engagement and burnout.

Furthermore, the existing literature exhibits abundant studies on organization engagement, which displays a major distinction between work engagement and organization engagement, with different strengths of relationships with other constructs (Farndale et al., 2014; Saks, 2019). However, it lacks a comprehensive understanding of the role of organization engagement between work engagement and burnout. Organization engagement is viewed to be more strongly related to the consequences of job engagement (Saks, 2020). Organization engagement is one of the strongest indicators of low employee turnover when compared to work engagement (Saks, 2006). It also partially mediates between a supportive work environment and employee retention, which is a stronger predictor of work engagement (Kundu et al., 2017), and fully mediates between perceived supervisor support and intention to quit which strongly predicts burnout (Torabi et al., 2019). Several studies have explored the role of various mediating and moderating variables in the relationship between work engagement and burnout (Tan & Yeap, 2021; Tu et al., 2022; Fastje et al., 2023; Bilginoglu & Yozgat, 2020; Garcia-Sierra et al., 2016; Cotter & Fouad., 2013). However, research examining burnout as a consequence of work engagement has not systematically explored the interplay with organization engagement between them. Therefore, we propose to study the mediating role of organization between work engagement and burnout as depicted in the conceptual model mentioned below in Figure 3, because work engagement and organization engagement have a moderate positive correlation, and organization engagement and job burnout may possibly have a negative relationship. The assumption of a negative relationship between organization engagement and job burnout is based on: 1. The positive relationship between organization engagement and work engagement and 2. the predominant negative correlation between work engagement and job burnout.

Figure 3: Potential mediation of organization engagement between work engagement and burnout

Implications

The study implores practitioners to be wary of the intricate and dynamic relationship between work engagement and burnout; work engagement can both lead to and reduce burnout. Therefore, there is a possibility that practitioners might inadvertently contribute to an increase in burnout levels while attempting to enhance employee engagement. Furthermore, they must consider the importance of organizational engagement, which has significant potential to enhance engagement levels. Key factors include the organization's corporate social responsibility, public service motivation, enabling bureaucracy, employer brand attributes and reputation, perceived organizational and supervisory support, and employees' voice and justice.

Future Research Directions

Our review highlights that in some cases work engagement and burnout coexist, therefore future studies may explore the reason for the coexistence of work engagement and burnout. They may use latent profile analysis to identify various classes of varying degrees of engagement and burnout, and qualitatively assess the reasons behind them. As indicated above, the relationship between organization engagement and burnout, and the mediating role of organization engagement between work engagement and burnout can be empirically investigated. Given that out of 75 research articles in this systematic literature review, 68 have utilized the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) developed by Schaufeli and Bakker (2002), which does not assess organization engagement as a distinct construct from work engagement (Saks, 2019; 2022), there is a recognized gap. Therefore, to comprehensively gauge engagement, it is crucial to develop a measurement scale that captures both work and organizational engagement. Alternatively, a separate measurement scale specifically designed to assess organizational engagement can be developed.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between engagement and burnout cannot always be predicted to be similar. Their relationship varies depending on the context, job environment, the availability of several job demands and resources, and employees' appraisal of the job demands. Therefore, to understand the inconsistencies in the correlation between

work engagement and burnout, it is crucial to focus on other factors that influence the relationship between engagement and burnout.

Limitations

Despite best efforts to conduct a comprehensive review in alignment with the established standards, this study includes some limitations. The primary constraint of this review is that not all available studies were considered. The sole reliance on a single database (Scopus) was employed with search restricted to titles, abstracts, keywords, and English language of search string results. Consequently, it is possible that pertinent studies were missed.

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